

Harsh Reality of Childhood in Toni Morrison's *God Help the Child*

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Abstract

Morrison's God Help the Child is published in 2015, is narration by a girl protagonist. She is led to query her self-constructed adult identity and to address her past. In the course of the story, Bride's body is textually foregrounded as the privileged site for the building of her identity, where the signs of an identity crisis will appear as symptoms of a childhood trauma. This article aims at analyzing how the novel's revelatory structure links the actually unrelated transformations undergone by Bride's body into a single narrative of secrecy and trauma. The novel draws on black feminism, gender studies, trauma studies, and an attempt to bridge the gap between two apparently different aspects: the thematic importance of the main character's body and the peculiarities of the narrative arrangement used to tell the story.

Keywords: Trauma, body, womanhood, child abuse secret.

God Help the Child is a persuasive novel where one can feel the splendor just beyond the reach. The characters and storytelling are utterly influential, but too much is exasperatingly defective. The novel describes the shape of a far grander book, where the characters are more fully travel around is far more at risk. The characters only can know the depth or significance of Bride, Sweetness, lesser extent, and Booker. Others can learn little so the narrative clearly demands much more. Sub-plots are prove that a deceitful co-worker and friend, Brooklyn that completes little. One of the characters who might appear the ripest for more growth, Queen, graces valuable few pages only. Yet still, there is the majesty, flaming beneath the surface of every word. The language, shifts in point of view and the brave of the novel's principles are overwhelming. Morrison remains a powerful writer. She concentrates on attention and no matter the story.

In *God Help the Child*, the story of an adult woman's in arrested growth. In Ernest Hemingway on Writing, the bearded misanthropist famously asked: "What is the best early training for a writer?" The answer is: "An unhappy childhood." (GHTC) (15). In that case, the characters in 84-years-old Toni Morrison's *God Help the Child* holds all the Nobel prize-winning authors like their creator and indeed Hemingway himself.

The direct of Morrison's lean 11th novel includes a woman Bride, who was as eager for maternal affection as a child that she tells an overwhelming lie to win her mother's attraction. Brooklyn, Bride's

best friend, is so toughened by her determining years that she seduces her friend's boyfriend and taken her job. The boyfriend, Booker, had his youth hasten into pieces by the murder of his older brother, Adam. The planned behind cast contain child molesters getting away with murder and a deserted girl rescued from the streets after run away her mother's offensive relationships.

The first section of the novel is divided into a series of monologues, conquered by Bride, and fleshed out by her mother, Sweetness, and Brooklyn. The opening stages feel harshly like Morrison caricature Morrison. The split is caused by her skin colour, which is significantly blacker than that of her parents. It asks likewise challenging questions of American acceptance and fairness:

"It didn't take more than an hour after they pulled her out from between my legs to realize that something was wrong, really wrong. She was so black she scared me. Midnight black. Sudanese black" (GHTC 56).

Questionably the critical plot describes, however, is driven by a instant of noncompliance when Bride's need for maternal love motivates her to tell a lie. This disloyalty of her primary value system is mirrored as she changes her name in the hunt for an important identity. Her affection for masks becomes something of a benefit in her business life. She becomes a success, a little bluntly, in marketing a cosmetic line called "You, Girl". The name is given to her by the love of that week, a apparently arty mystery named Booker, who loves her skin quality in quite sinister fashion. Black is the new black, he tells to her persuasively, before instructs her to be dressed in nothing but white. "You're more Hershey's syrup than licorice. Makes people think of whipped cream and chocolate soufflé every time they see you" (GHTC 58).

God Help the Child is an odd, fascinating but strangely indefinable novel. The narrative machinations, moving from the first person to a third person epic as Bride pursues Booker and herself. The voices prove rough while Sweetness is superbly dreadful - vanity made flesh - Bride is less persuasive. "Would someone that hip, cool and youthful use the word "pudenda"? Her story too is doled out in lumpy spoonfuls, with quite a lot of slop (Brooklyn, Sofia Huxley) simply falling out of view onto the floor. As the title suggests, the novel's heart is obviously in the correct place. Stress "God", and it sounds like an appeal for sympathy in a world that says it loves children then throw away, mistreatment, abandon and kills them.

The old wicked Sweetness returns full strangle when she find out Booker and Bride are going to have a baby of their own. Her narrow-minded just-you-wait unpleasantness is too bad to be true: "Listen to me. You are about to find out what it takes, how the world is, how it works and how it changes when you are a parent" (GHTC 107). But unluckily, *God Help the Child* takes only a light echo of that earlier novel's influence. The tale revolves around a successful cosmetics designer who calls herself Bride.

The instability is more severe at the novel's center. Bride meets just after her lover, Booker, has peremptorily rejects her. "If thoughts like that strike you as both fresh and somehow eternal, you're in luck: There are a lot of them here" (). The upset of Bride's misfortune causes her to lose her pubic hair. Soon her earring holes close up, her period stops and then her breasts shrink. In the semi-magical worlds Morrison has produced before, such strange touches appear both reminiscent and oddly natural, but in the plane language of this novel, they're clunky signs, unnecessarily explain about changing back into a little black girl. It doesn't help that Bride and Booker's romantic travels which are not chiefly convincing are predicated on much more dramatic stories of pedophilia and murder in their pasts.

This interlude is astonishing, expressively multifaceted and oval without being sketchy. It's everything, in other words, the rest of this novel should be. In spite of being a very winning focused, Bride as she prefers to be known is troubled by her unlikable reminiscences of her childhood. For example, the countless instances of sadism or of child abuse such as witnessing the rape of a young

boy by their landowner. As an adult too she is ill-treated and comes crossways other victims such as Rain. It is as if this drain of violence simultaneous with “normal” life is a given. There is a instant when Bride hopes that she can be right or wrong. She is in her childhood with a consequence she does not expect. While getting better from the incident, Bride concludes to set off on a pursuit in search of her boyfriend, Booker, who left from her life.

God Help the Child is a well merge of all that is well-known in Toni Morrison’s novels and interviews. Morrison’s obsession with depiction of women is black culture and their history, race and child abuse. Her well skill as a master craftsperson proves in the novel. There is a suggestion of magic realism in the storytelling along with the certain play of diverse narratives, juxtaposed in a manner that jerk the reader into understanding none of the narrators can be relied upon. Yet, every voice that tells their description of actions is a strong behavior. It is probable to envisage the speaker, particularly the women, obviously whether it is Booker’s elderly and kind aunt Queen, Bride’s mother Sweetness, ex-convict Sofia, or child prostitute Rain. The ending of the novel is frightening with its troubling note, ironically understood in conditions that offer optimism.

To conclude, *God Help the Child* displays major hope. There is no doubt that the psychological and affecting childhood blemish that dwells in this narrative are somehow finally predetermined. Most of the main characters, true survivors of child abuse, skill a purifying modification in their lives. Rain finds in the hippy couple the choice of rising up and remedial from her childhood injury. All the characters of Morrison one way or another, carry the burden of childhood pain: “[A] set of connections, which extend from her [Bride] to Booker and on to a semi-feral girl named Rain [. . .]: a cycle of abuse, of molestation” (Ulin, 2015). Morrison “carefully explores the nature of victimhood and the consequences of domestic violence through a series of fascinating and believable narrators.” (Iqbal, 2015). Toni Morrison does not hide from exposing the harsh realities children face, and how the shocking past is continuously influencing their lives. *God Help the Child* is a tribute to all the innumerable victims of domestic cruelty, an continuing dreadful drama that has no end.

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